

A descriptive study to assess the knowledge regarding neonatal care among spouses of primigravida women in Kamla Nehru state hospital, Shimla (H.P)

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Abstract:

Title of the Study - “A Descriptive Study to Assess the Knowledge Regarding Neonatal Care among Spouses of Primigravida Women in Kamla Nehru State Hospital, Shimla”. Major advisor: Mrs. Vindhya Thakur, Assistant Professor Akal College of Nursing. Introduction: Neonatal care encompasses the vital support provided to a newborn, whether by the mother or a caregiver, including breastfeeding, maintaining body temperature, caring for the umbilical cord, eye care, and preventing infections and injuries. The first week after birth is a critical period of metabolic and physiological adjustment for newborns as they transition to life outside the womb. This phase is challenging for neonates as they attempt to adapt to their new environment. During this crucial time, they require specialized care, close monitoring, and support to ensure a smooth adaptation process. Aim of the study: The aim of the study is to assess the level of knowledge regarding neonatal care among spouse of primigravida women in Kamla Nehru state hospital of district Shimla Himachal Pradesh. Methods and Materials: A non- experimental research design with quantitative research approach was used to assess the knowledge regarding neonatal care among spouse of primigravida women in Kamla Nehru State Hospital of district Shimla Himachal Pradesh. Non probability convenience sampling technique was used sample xi size of 52 spouses of primigravida women. Self- structured questionnaire was used for data collection. Results: The findings revealed that the majority of the spouses of primigravida women were having adequate knowledge (65.4%), less than half were having moderately adequate knowledge (32.7%) and the very few were having poor knowledge (1.9%). The association between socio demographic variables and the level of knowledge of spouses of primigravida women, the significant association was only found with area of residence $\chi^2=9.532$, $p=0.039$) other socio demographic variables such as age, religion, educational qualification, occupation, income and type of family was not associated with level of knowledge. Conclusion: The study was related to assess the level of knowledge regarding neonatal care among the spouses of primigravida women admitted in Kamla Nehru Hospital State Hospital, District Shimla (H.P). The study findings revealed that the majority of the spouses of primigravida women were having Adequate knowledge (65.4%), & less than half were having moderately adequate knowledge (32.7%) and a very few were having inadequate knowledge (1.9%).

Keywords:

Assess, knowledge, primigravida women.

1. Introduction:

“Mother is the purest form of source from whom even greatest take birth| Neonatal care encompasses the vital support provided to a newborn, whether by the mother or a caregiver, including breastfeeding, maintaining body

temperature, caring for the umbilical cord, eye care, and preventing infections and injuries. The first week after birth is a critical period of metabolic and physiological adjustment for newborns as they transition to life outside the womb. This phase is challenging for neonates as they attempt to adapt to their new environment. During this crucial time, they require specialized care, close monitoring, and support to ensure a smooth adaptation process.¹ Every newborn, everywhere, has the right to receive high-quality, universal health care. Babies are entitled to protection from injury and infection, the ability to breathe freely, warmth, and proper nutrition. All newborns should have access to essential newborn care, which includes the crucial care required during the first few days after birth. This care starts immediately at birth and continues throughout the entire newborn period. It is essential both in health facilities and at home. Neonatal care refers to the specialized care provided to premature or sick babies in a neonatal unit, which is part of a hospital dedicated to supporting newborns immediately after birth. The term "neonatal" refers to the first 28 days of a baby's life. In the UK, over 90,000 babies are born prematurely or with health conditions each year, requiring neonatal care. It is believed that you having a baby in neonatal care can stir up a wide range of emotions, some of which can be difficult to cope with. It may feel anxious about why the newborn was born prematurely or sick, or about the treatments they are receiving.² Fathers play a crucial role in the care team during labor and delivery at the Family Birth Centre. They offer vital emotional support to their partner, which may involve advocating for their birth plan or communicating their partner's needs to the medical staff. Fathers can also keep other family members updated and help coordinate care for older children. It's important for fathers to feel supported as well—they should feel comfortable asking questions throughout the process to better understand and feel confident in their role. In the early days of a baby's life, fathers can offer consistent nurturing and care, which forms the foundation of the lasting bond they will share with their child. Even before birth, babies become familiar with their father's voice. Fathers can read or talk to their baby, strengthening this connection and promoting language development. Additionally, fathers can contribute by changing diapers, offering bottle feeds, and engaging in activities like rocking, holding (including skin-to-skin care), soothing, and playing with their newborn.³

1.1. Background of the study:

The first 28 days of life, known as the neonatal period, are the most critical and vulnerable for a child's survival. Worldwide, around 2.6 million children die within the first month of life, with approximately 7,000 neonates dying every day, most of these deaths occurring within the first week. Neonatal mortality is a major contributor to the overall number of under-five deaths (WHO, 2016). Each of these deaths is a heartbreaking tragedy, especially since many of them are preventable. The Kingdom of Eswatini faces high neonatal mortality rates, currently at 20 per 1,000 live births (MICS 2014). As a nation, we are committed to reducing these rates through dedicated efforts, implementing essential health interventions, and working toward the global Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) target of fewer than 10 deaths per 1,000 live births by 2030, while eliminating preventable neonatal deaths. The launch of our national neonatal care clinical guidelines marks a significant step in ensuring that all neonates receive the highest standard of care and the best possible start in life. These guidelines, developed from various global sources and adapted to the country's health practices, are designed to provide healthcare providers with a framework for delivering consistent, high-quality neonatal care across the nation.⁴ A descriptive qualitative study design was employed, guided by the Theory of Planned Behavior and Lamb's model on male involvement. In June 2021, sixteen in depth interviews were conducted with fathers of preterm infants, who were purposively and conveniently selected. The interviews were digitally recorded and transcribed verbatim. Data were organized and analyzed using NVivo software, with 3 thematic analyses applied to explore the data in depth, identify patterns and themes, and gain rich insights into the participants' experiences and perspectives. The study revealed that fathers highly value their role in caring for hospitalized preterm newborns, but they encounter several challenges. Evidence-based interventions, such as educational programs, training sessions, and support groups, can help fathers overcome these obstacles and contribute to improved outcomes for both infants and families.⁵

The majority of neonatal deaths (75%) occur during the first week of life, with approximately 1 million newborns dying within the first 24 hours. The leading causes of neonatal death include premature birth, birth complications (such as birth asphyxia and trauma), neonatal infections, and congenital anomalies, which together account for nearly 40% of all child deaths under the age of five. Despite a global decline in the rates of these leading causes since 2000, they still represent the same proportion—four in ten—of under-five deaths in both 2000 and 2022. Access to quality healthcare remains a critical factor in the survival of mothers and newborns worldwide, with the vast majority of newborn deaths occurring in low- and middle-income countries. Efforts to improve newborn survival must be based on a strong foundation of essential neonatal care, in line with Every Newborn Action Plan (ENAP) and Ending Preventable Maternal Mortality (EPMM) target, which focus on antenatal care, postnatal care, skilled health personnel, and emergency obstetric and neonatal care.

Increasing funding and resources for two high-impact, high-cost interventions—care for small and sick newborns and emergency obstetric care—are vital, as they offer significant returns on investment by reducing maternal deaths, stillbirths, newborn deaths, and both maternal and newborn morbidity. In areas with well-established midwifery programs, providing midwife-led continuity of care (MLCC) has been shown to reduce preterm births by up to 24%. MLCC is a care model in which a midwife or a team of midwives provide continuous care throughout pregnancy, childbirth, and the postnatal period, with medical support as needed. With the rise in facility-based births (nearly 80% globally), there is a significant opportunity to provide essential newborn care and identify and manage high-risk newborns. However, many women and newborns do not stay in the facility for the recommended 24 hours after birth, which is a critical period when complications can arise. Furthermore, too many newborns die at home due to early discharge from the hospital, barriers to access, and delays in seeking care. The four recommended postnatal care visits, whether at health facilities or through home visits, are crucial in reaching these newborns and their families. To accelerate progress in neonatal survival and promote health and well-being, it is essential to enhance the quality of care and ensure that quality health services are available for small and sick newborns.⁷

1.2. Problem statement of the study a descriptive study to assess the knowledge regarding neonatal care:

Among Spouse of Primigravida Women in Kamla Nehru State Hospital of District Shimla Himachal Pradesh

1.3 objectives of the study:

To assess the knowledge regarding neonatal care among spouse of primigravida women.

To determine the association between knowledge score with selected socio demographic variables of spouses of primigravida women.

1.4. Operational definition:

1. Assess: It refers to the act of determining knowledge regarding neonatal care by self-structured questionnaire.
2. Knowledge: It refers to the information possessed by spouse regarding neonatal care measured through structured questionnaire.
3. Neonatal care: It refers to the care given to the neonate in the first 28 days of life regarding breastfeeding, hygiene, immunization, warmth, safety measures, safe sleep practices & traditional taboos.
4. Spouse: It refers to the legally married male partner of a primi gravida mother.
5. Primigravida women: It refers to the women who are pregnant for the first time & have visited Kamla Nehru State Hospital Shimla.

1.5. Assumptions:

All the spouse of primigravida may provide correct information about their knowledge regarding neonatal care. The spouse of primigravida women may have adequate knowledge about neonatal care.

1.6. Delimitations of the study:

Study is delimited to the spouses of primigravida women in Kamla Nehru State Hospital of District Shimla Himachal Pradesh.

2. Methodology:

The study used a quantitative research approach with a descriptive design and was conducted at Kamla Nehru State Hospital, while the pilot study was carried out at Indira Gandhi Medical College and Hospital. Demographic variables included age, religion, education, occupation, income, family type, and area of residence. The target population consisted of spouses of primigravida women, and 52 participants were selected using convenient non-probability sampling. Data were collected using a self-structured questionnaire containing socio-demographic details and 35 knowledge-based questions on breastfeeding, hygiene, immunization, warmth, safe sleep practices, traditional taboos, and safety measures. The tool was validated by nursing experts and found reliable with an r-value of 0.728. Ethical permission was obtained from the concerned authorities, and confidentiality of participants was maintained throughout the study.

3. Results:

Section A: Distribution of characteristics of spouses of primigravida women.

Table: 4.1 Percentage distribution of spouses of primigravida women based on their socio demographic variables.
N=52

S. No.	Socio-demographic variables	f	%
1.	Age in years		
	21-25	11	21.2
	26-30	22	42.3
	31-35	12	23.1
	>35	7	13.5
2.	Religion		
	Hinduism	52	100
	Islam	0	0
	Sikhism	0	0
	Christianity	0	0
3.	Educational qualification		
	No formal education	0	0
	Primary education	1	1.9
	Secondary education	7	13.5
	High school	19	36.5
	Graduate	14	26.9
	Post graduate	11	21.2
4.	Occupation		
	Government employee	14	26.9
	Private employee	19	36.5
	Farmer	13	25
	Self employed	6	11.5
5.	Income		
	Rs. <5000	6	11.5
	Rs.5001-10000	5	9.6
	Rs.10001-20000	19	36.5
	Rs.20001-50000	16	30.8
	Rs. >50000	6	11.5
6.	Type of family		
	Nuclear	14	26.9
	Joint	36	69.2
	Extended	2	3.8
7.	Area of residence		
	Rural	45	86.5
	Urban	4	7.7
	Semi-urban	3	5.8

Tab. 4.1. This table depicts that more than half of the participants (42.3%) were in the age group of 26–30 years. Nearly one-fourth (23.1%) were between 31–35 years, while 21.2% belonged to the 21–25 years age group. Only small proportions (13.5%) were above 35 years of age. All participants (100%) followed Hinduism. With regard to educational qualification, more than one-third (36.5%) had completed high school education. Nearly one-fourth (26.9%) were graduates; while slightly more than one-fifth (21.2%) had completed post-graduation. A smaller percentage (13.5%) had secondary education, and a very few (1.9%) had completed primary education. Occupationally, more than one-third (36.5%) were private employees, while about one-fourth (26.9%) were employed in government jobs. One-fourth (25%) of the participants were farmers, and a smaller proportion (11.5%) were self-employed. In terms of income, more than one-third (36.5%) had a monthly income ranging from ₹10,001 to ₹20,000, while nearly one-third (30.8%) earned between ₹20,001 and

₹50,000. Only a few participants (11.5%) earned either less than ₹5,000 or more than ₹50,000. Considering family type, more than two-thirds (69.2%) belonged to joint families, while around one-fourth (26.9%) were from nuclear families. Very small proportions (3.8%) were from extended families.

Section: B Distribution of knowledge on spouses of primigravida women.

Table: 4.2 Frequency and percentage distribution of scores of levels of knowledge.
N=52

Level of knowledge	Interpretation	f	%
Adequate	27-35	34	65.4
Moderately Adequate	18-26	17	32.7
Inadequate	9-17	1	1.9

Maximum score=35 Minimum score=9

Inference: Tab. 4.2 depicts Percentage distribution of level of knowledge among the spouses of primigravida women, the data revealed that the majority of the spouses of primigravida women were having adequate knowledge (65.4%), less than half were having adequate knowledge (32.7%) and very few were having poor knowledge (1.9%)

SECTION: C Association between the levels of knowledge among spouses of primigravida women with selected socio demographic variables.

Table: 4.3. The association between the levels of knowledge with selected socio demographic variables.
(n =52)

S.No	Socio-demographic variables	Adequate knowledge	Moderately Adequate knowledge	Inadequate knowledge	Fisher's exact test	p value
1.	Age in years				8.689	0.134
	21-25	0	7	4		
	26-30	1	7	14		
	31-35	0	2	10		
	>35	0	1	6		
2.	Religion					
	Hinduism	1	17	34		
	Islam	0	0	0		
	Sikhism	0	0	0		
	Christianity	0	0	0		
3.	Educational Qualification				7.821	0.698
	No formal education	0	0	0		
	Primary education	0	1	0		
	Secondary education	1	3	4		
	High school	0	6	12		
	Graduate	0	3	11		
	Post graduate	1	4	7		
4.	Occupation				5.828	0.474
	Government employee	0	5	9		
	Private employee	0	4	15		
	Farmer	1	5	7		
	Self employed	0	3	3		
5.	Income					
	Rs. <5000	0	2	4		
	Rs.5001-10000	1	2	2		
	Rs.10001-20000	0	7	12		

	Rs.20001- 50000	0	4	12	7.603	0.590
	Rs. >50000	0	2	4		
6.	Type of Family				3.378	0.696
	Nuclear	0	6	8		
	Joint	1	11	24		
	Extended	0	0	2		
7.	Area of Residence*				9.532	0.039*
	Rural	0	16	29		
	Urban	0	0	4		
	Semi-urban	1	1	1		

*= Significant ($p < 0.05$)

NS=non-significant ($p > 0.05$)

Tab. 4.3. shows the association between socio demographic variables and the level of knowledge of spouses of primigravida women, the significant association was only found with area of residence $\chi^2=9.532$, $p=0.039$ other socio demographic variables such as age, religion, educational qualification, occupation, income and type of family was not associated with level of knowledge.

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